

**NATIONAL EVOLUTIONARY SYNTHESIS CENTER
YEAR 4 SITE VISIT SELF STUDY REPORT
FEBRUARY 2008**

www.nescent.org

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Introduction	4
Part 1 – A brief overview of NESCent’s accomplishments years 1-3	5
A. Synthetic science at the Center	5
NESCent brings together scientists from diverse fields in order to create new conceptual and analytic approaches to important questions	
NESCent provides a stimulating environment for theoretical breakthroughs	
NESCent stimulates new synthetic analyses of important evolutionary questions	
B. Creating and supporting a culture of sharing and collaboration	7
NESCent is changing the collaborative culture of biological disciplines	
NESCent promotes emerging standards for evolutionary biology databases	
NESCent builds community consensus and the necessary technical infrastructure for widespread data sharing	
NESCent promotes open-source software development for evolutionary synthesis	
C. Education: the evolutionary biology community, K-16 and the public	10
NESCent supports a unique postdoctoral community	
NESCent is helping to train the next generation of synthetic researchers	
NESCent is promoting collaborative solutions for effective K-16 evolution education	
D. Partnering with the broader community	12
NESCent promotes science in the local community	
NESCent partners with other organizations to advance major scientific initiatives	
Part 2 – Some facts and figures	14
A. The nature of NESCent science	14
B. Outcomes	15
C. Demographics of NESCent supported activities	16
D. Grants and broader activities	17

E. NESCent activities towards the recruitment of underserved groups	17
F. Operations and administration	17
Part 3 – Looking forward	20
A. Evaluating our transformative impact	20
B. Continuing to broaden outreach and impact within and beyond the core evolutionary biology community.	20
C. Attracting applicants, particularly postdocs, from a diverse pool	21
D. Maintaining a continuously vibrant community of sabbatical scholars and bringing a diverse array of scientists to the Center	22
E. Continually obtaining broad community input	23
F. NESCent initiated programs and activities	24
G. Administrative issues	24
H. Looking forward	25
Appendices	
Appendix 1. Visitors to the NESCent years 1-3	26
List of funded project titles years 1-3	27
Appendix 2. Center partnerships and associations	33
Appendix 3. Demographics of Applicants	37
Demographic data on funded scientists	38
Graphs of gender, residency and ethnic and racial data	39
Appendix 4. Residency of funded scientists: U.S.	43
Residency of international scientists	45
Appendix 5. Funded external grants and proposals	47
Appendix 6. Activities towards the recruitment of underserved groups	49
Appendix 7. NESCent organizational chart	52
Appendix 8. Web traffic	53
Appendix 9. Meetings attended (outreach)	55
Appendix 10. Advertisements for call for proposals	57

INTRODUCTION

NESCent's mission is to enable synthetic research in evolutionary biology. Our primary task is to facilitate innovative, interdisciplinary, and ultimately paradigm changing research through the funding of investigator-initiated proposals. We bring creative and highly motivated scientists to the Center and provide them with an atmosphere in which they can maximize scientific collaboration and productivity. We work to bring all sub-disciplines of evolutionary biology together; we also hope to engage fields that are not normally associated with evolutionary thinking. We expect that ultimately NESCent sponsored activities will both transform and propel evolutionary science.

We expect to take the lead in constructing new analytic tools for evolutionary biology, in promoting accessibility and interoperability of current tools, in assembling and analyzing novel databases, and in training scientists and students in the field of informatics which is so important for researchers in the current information age. A major goal is to change the culture of data sharing in evolutionary biology. To that end we are working with societies, journals and a variety of other groups to establish the infrastructure so that data deposition and sharing can become a required and accepted part of the publication process.

NESCent aims to increase the public understanding of science by making current research in evolutionary biology accessible to a broad audience. We work to develop quality resources for educators at all levels, and to disseminate widely the resources we, as well as others, have developed. As we move toward our broader goals, we work to broaden the demographics of evolutionary biology and to support and recruit individuals from groups that are not currently well represented in our field. As a measure of our impact we have established collaborations and partnerships nationally and internationally, so that NESCent has become a central resource and broker for a wide range of organizations involved in evolutionary biology.

During the first three years of NESCent's existence we have worked hard to establish a Center to achieve these goals, and we believe we have been fundamentally successful in doing so. In a brief report, we cannot detail all our activities and achievements. In this self study we highlight a few major accomplishments and provide a basis to begin the conversation.

This report is divided into three major parts. Part 1 is a narrative that attempts to illustrate the types of activities that have been a focus of NESCent's efforts. This is of course not comprehensive. Instead we highlight our achievements with specific examples of how we meet our multi-faceted mission. We organize this material to highlight our major contributions in enabling synthetic science; creating a culture of sharing and collaboration; educating the scientific community and the public; and broader partnerships.

Part 2 revisits some of these issues with some facts and figures. We also update data provided in our previous annual reports.

Finally, Part 3 discusses new initiatives already in place, others in the planning stage, and fundamental questions that we face as we look forward. Additionally, in parts 2 & 3 we address key issues raised in the previous site visit.

PART 1

A BRIEF OVERVIEW OF NESCENT'S ACCOMPLISHMENTS IN YEARS 1-3.

A. Synthetic science at the Center

NESCent brings together scientists from diverse fields in order to create new conceptual and analytic approaches to important questions.

Major research challenges often require the integration of data, tools and perspectives from multiple communities of researchers. NESCent sponsors a large number of meetings designed to bring diverse individuals together to the Center (Appendix 1). In particular, **catalysis meetings** provide a novel mechanism for bringing together diverse research communities and cultures. These meetings typically involve 30-40 participants and focus on identifying common interests, productive questions, available data and potential directions for synthesis. Although we initially planned to support catalysis meetings only in our first year of operation, they have been so popular and successful in enabling synthesis that they are now an important component of our ongoing research portfolio.

As one example, recent and ongoing advances in human genomics are providing an unprecedented view of human genetic variation. Steve Stearns, Peter Byers and Raju Govindaraju organized a catalysis meeting entitled “**Evolution in contemporary human populations: medical, genetic and behavioral implications**” bringing together physicians, geneticists, epidemiologists, ethicists, anthropologists, and evolutionary biologists. They focused on two main questions: First what evolutionary questions of medical significance can be addressed by integrating data from epidemiological studies with emerging data from the human genome, HapMap and related projects, and second, how should future long-term studies be designed to address such evolutionary questions? The meeting facilitated a number of new research collaborations that have coalesced into specific projects. A successful NESCent working group project, led by Govindaraju, Stearns, Andy Clark and Trudy Mackay, is combining SNP and other genetic and genomic data to analyze evolutionary patterns in data generated from the three-generation US Framingham Heart Study. Another project, led by Magdalena Hurtado and Peter Ellison, will analyze existing biomedical data to document evolutionary change in indigenous populations.

This example illustrates how catalysis meetings can bring together different research communities to generate new collaborations. Importantly, it helped bring medical researchers into a focused evolutionary biology arena. Other catalysis meetings have also generated new working groups and collaborations. For example, the “**Integrated studies of genetic networks**” meeting (organized by Stephen Proulx) generated a successful working group on “**Modeling variation in gene networks**” (Paul Magwene and David Houle). Catalysis meetings on “**Biodiversity in Madagascar**” (Anne Yoder and Claire Kremen) and on “**Myelin as model for evolutionary innovation**” (Daniel Hartline) have also generated recent working group proposals and new collaborations. Several catalysis meetings on emerging model organisms have been important in promoting NESCent's leadership in GMOD (see below). A complete list of NESCent funded projects in years 1-3 can be found in Appendix 1.

NESCent provides a stimulating environment for theoretical breakthroughs.

Mathematical models provide the fundamental theoretical framework for modern evolutionary biology. While the creation of such models can take place in any environment, recent sabbatical

and Triangle scholars at NESCent have been particularly successful in producing important theoretical advances during their stay.

For example, genetic mutations occur in all organisms, and many mutations impact fitness, but the relative frequency of harmful, neutral and beneficial mutations, and the strength of their effects on fitness are not known. These issues are at the heart of a wide range of fundamental genetic and evolutionary issues, from genetic medical disorders, to the nature of adaptation and the evolution of sex. The recent explosion of data on DNA sequence variation within and between populations provides a powerful new resource for exploring the fitness consequences of mutations. During his year at NESCent **Sabbatical Scholar Adam Eyre-Walker** developed new theoretical models that estimate the frequency distribution of fitness effects. A major advance of these models is that they account for potential effects of demographic (population size) changes. Eyre-Walker has applied this new method to a dataset of human genes. This and related work at NESCent by Eyre-Walker has generated 8 publications in *Science*, *PNAS*, *Nature Review Genetics*, *Genetics*, *TREE* and other top journals.

Most theoretical models in evolutionary biology focus on the processes within populations or sets of populations within a species. Interactions between species—competition, predation, parasitism, mutualism, etc.—are critical in evolution, but are typically incorporated implicitly in theoretical models (for example, as selection coefficients). **Sabbatical Scholar Sally Otto** spent a year at NESCent working to incorporate species interactions explicitly into evolutionary models. Her project developed a comprehensive theoretical framework for understanding how and when species interactions alter the rate and mode of evolution of a species, and identified traits whose evolution will be strongly influenced by species interactions. This project was extraordinarily productive, already resulting in 11 publications in *Genetics*, *TREE*, *Proceedings of the Royal Society*, *PLoS Genetics*, *The American Naturalist*, *Cell* and other top journals.

NESCent stimulates new synthetic analyses of important evolutionary questions.

A central goal of research at NESCent is to synthesize data from multiple taxa, locations and habitats to identify and confirm general evolutionary patterns. Many of our working groups and postdoctoral fellows are conducting these meta-analytic syntheses; to illustrate we briefly describe two examples.

How common and strong is local adaptation in nature? **NESCent Postdoctoral Fellow Joe Hereford** conducted a synthesis and meta-analysis of experimental studies of local adaptation in natural populations to document the frequency and magnitude of local adaptation in natural populations. Using a defined set of criteria for types of study systems, experimental protocols and fitness measures, Hereford identified and collated 73 studies of local adaptation in natural populations for a variety of plant and animal species. His analyses demonstrate that local adaptation is quite common: in more than 70% of the study cases, local populations have greater fitness in their native habitats than all non-native populations. On average, native populations have 20-30% higher fitness than non-native populations, but there is substantial variation in this native advantage among species. There is little evidence thus far for publication bias in the analyses. Surprisingly, increasing gene flow among populations has no detectable effects on limiting the extent of local adaptation. These results are important for understanding local and regional patterns of biological diversity, the evolutionary potential of natural populations to respond to environmental change, and the resistance of native populations to biological invasion. Hereford also initiated a **collaboration with NESCent Postdoctoral Fellow Jason Hoeksema**, extending their analyses to include local adaptation in host-parasite interactions. These studies have generated 2 publications (*The American Naturalist* and *BioScience*). The opportunity to pursue such synthetic and independent research as a

postdoctoral fellow is almost unmatched within evolutionary biology. Since their NESCent fellowships, Hereford has begun a NSF Postdoctoral Fellowship at the University of Maryland, and Hoeksema a faculty position at Mississippi State.

Theoretical models predict that the mating system of a plant species should be either primarily selfing or primarily outcrossing. However, more than 40% of insect-pollinated flowering plants reproduce through a mixture of selfing and outcrossing (mixed-mating). Why are mixed-mating systems so common in plants and what are the consequences of this for diversification and trait evolution in flowering plants? **A Working Group organized by Susan Kalisz and Mark Johnston, “Understanding the paradox of mixed mating,”** is resolving this gap between current theoretical predictions and empirical evidence. One product of the group is a major new database on selfing rates in plants. The database includes more than 1300 mating system estimates, and incorporates data on inbreeding depression, life history, floral morphological traits and other information, chosen to integrate with the ecological, genetic and evolutionary parameters relevant to theoretical model predictions. Combined with new theoretical models and phylogenetic adjustments for testing the relationship of selfing rate to other biological features, the database is being used to test a variety of questions about how evolution of selfing affects trait evolution, pollination, and evolutionary diversification. The group led to a successful symposium at the 2007 SSE meetings in New Zealand, and has already generated 5 published or submitted papers (5 more in preparation) in *The American Naturalist*, *Systematic Biology*, *Journal of Theoretical Biology*, and *Journal of Evolutionary Biology*.

B. Creating and supporting a culture of sharing and collaboration

NESCent is changing the collaborative culture of biological disciplines.

The extent and types of collaborative research vary widely among disciplines and sub-disciplines within biology. For example, collaborative, synthetic research is currently much more widespread within phylogenetics and genomics than within animal physiology or neurobiology. A major goal for NESCent is to facilitate the cultural changes needed to expand data sharing and community synthesis. An ongoing **working group on primate life histories, organized by Karen Strier, Anne Pusey and Susan Alberts**, illustrates how these cultural barriers to synthetic research can be reduced. This working group, jointly sponsored by NESCent and NCEAS, has brought together Principal Investigators of long-term field studies of primates in wild populations, along with demographers and population modelers. Typically PIs in this field work independently, and do not share underlying datasets, making it difficult to identify general commonalities and differences in primate life histories. During their first two group meetings, the participants have developed templates and criteria for standardizing data across systems, and worked with the NESCent informatics staff to develop a relational database structure that incorporates biography, population, and female fertility data; data entry is now ongoing, using an interface developed by NESCent. The resulting database will allow new synthetic and comparative analyses about the roles of phylogeny, ecology, environment, and behavior in shaping patterns of mortality, fertility and aging in primates—analyses not possible without the sustained collaborative efforts of this NESCent group.

Beyond working with individual groups of scientists, NESCent is taking a number of major steps to provide the infrastructure for data sharing across evolutionary biology. This includes several important initiatives.

NESCent promotes emerging standards for evolutionary biology databases.

Because of the dramatic increase in the efficiency and accessibility of technologies for genome sequencing and the acquisition of other forms of genomic data, genome projects are no longer restricted to a small number of model organisms. In recent years, many genome projects have been undertaken with an explicitly evolutionary motivation (in species closely related to genome models, in popular evolutionary genetics models, and species occupying critical phylogenetic positions). NESCent has played an important role enabling emerging model organism communities to define their research and infrastructure goals. The Center has sponsored two catalysis meetings (“**Developing new model systems for evolutionary genomics using Poeciliid fishes**” and “**Genomic approaches to the study of adaptive radiation**”), a sabbatical project (“**Relational evolutionary database for *Heliconius* butterflies**”), and hosted a meeting and two Triangle scholars for the project “**Integrated ecological and genomic analysis of speciation in *Mimulus***.”

The widespread promotion of informatics standards and best practices for management and dissemination of genomic data requires the advocacy of an organization such as NESCent. Through active participation in the **Generic Model Organism Database Project** (GMOD; www.gmod.org), NESCent is playing a leadership role in creating community consensus around a long-term vision for evolutionary genome informatics. GMOD is an open-source software development effort to produce a diverse array of highly-configurable, powerful, off-the-shelf solutions for data management and dissemination. The large community of developers allows feature requests and bugs to be addressed soon after they arise, reducing the maintenance and upkeep costs on individual user groups. The use of common database modules also facilitates interoperability and database federation. NESCent has external funding from the NIH to provide end-user support for GMOD (see http://www.gmod.org/wiki/index.php/GMOD_Help_Desk), and actively promotes its adoption. NESCent has also worked with its sponsored scientists and with the larger community to modify the Chado database schema and make it more useful for managing data about genetic variation in natural populations.

NESCent builds community consensus and the necessary technical infrastructure for widespread data sharing.

A limiting factor in the ability to do synthetic science is the availability of data from previous investigations. While specialized repositories exist for some data types (e.g. DNA sequences, phylogenetic trees), data underlying most published works in evolutionary biology are not made available for examination or reuse by others. The poor response obtained when investigators personally request supporting data from the author of a previously published paper is well documented, and authors are not taking advantage of available options for sharing data. For example, in a random sample of papers from five evolutionary biology journals published in 2006 and 2007, we found that less than half provided the supporting data in any form, while more than three quarters of the papers relied on previously published data for their own conclusions. Thus, currently investigators are using shared data more often than they are sharing data, themselves.

In collaboration with a consortium of societies and journals (listed in the Annual Report), NESCent is working to enable a scientific culture of data sharing by implementing a **digital data repository named Dryad** (www.datadryad.org; see <http://driade.nescent.org> for information on the full project). This repository will be closely coupled with the publication process. If the plan is successful, submission of data in Dryad will be required for publication in a wide spectrum of journals. Dryad, which is being developed through extensive consultations

with evolutionary biology stakeholders and experts from the information science community, is intended to ease the submission process for authors by reducing the burden of submitting data directly to multiple repositories (e.g. NCBI, TreeBase) and Dryad will also capture orphan data types that do not currently have a home. The platform will also provide persistent resolvable links to data, enable data citations, and allow sophisticated searches not only across journals but even across similar data and metadata repositories in related disciplines (e.g., ecology).

Dryad will help to democratize the availability of data (e.g., to investigators in the third world, and at small institutions). One section of the repository, being designed in collaboration with the BioQUEST consortium, is devoted to well-curated datasets of particular educational value with associated curriculum materials. Dryad is also a good example of how the three Triangle institutions are contributing to the success of the Center. The Metadata Research Center at the UNC Chapel Hill School of Information and Library Sciences has been a partner in the design of the system, it is being implemented by NESCent staff at Duke University, and plans call for the physical infrastructure to be managed by the renowned Digital Library program at NCSU.

Through Dryad, NESCent is capitalizing on its unique position within the community to have a positive transformative effect on evolutionary biology and to serve as a model for other scientific disciplines faced with similar data challenges. For many years journals and funding agencies have advocated data deposition. This effort will make it possible.

NESCent promotes open-source software development for evolutionary synthesis.

Evolutionary biologists have collectively developed and distributed hundreds of specialty software programs intended to enable users to perform a huge variety of computational analyses in systematics, population and quantitative genetics, molecular evolution, paleontology, and so on. Unfortunately, academic software programs are notorious for lacking regular maintenance and user support, being platform-specific, requiring idiosyncratic file formats, and having clunky interfaces. The software written by the evolutionary biology community is no exception.

In open software development, synthetic ideas often emerge from a diverse cacophony of contributions. While it is one thing for software to be open source, it is far more valuable for software to be collaboratively developed, poked, prodded, tested, critiqued and improved by a whole community. NESCent is in a unique position to promote just such an open development model for its scientific community, and has been doing so through several activities. These efforts lead to software that is better engineered, better documented, better maintained, and conforms better to interface and data exchange standards. Open development also leads to community consensus as to where development effort should be focused, and by so doing avoids reinvention of the wheel.

One of NESCent's most original and important contributions to this end is the "**hackathon**" concept. Hackathons are working meetings in which participants collaboratively write code, contributing to shared software libraries (e.g. in R or BioPerl) that have wide application. NESCent has so far organized two of these unique, intensely productive, meetings (see Annual Report and <http://hackathon.nescent.org> for details). Our second hackathon, held in December 2007 on "**Comparative Phylogenetic Methods in R,**" is notable for having been initially proposed through a whitepaper by two NESCent postdocs, Sam Price and Amy Zanne; a third NESCent postdoc, Brian O'Meara, later joined as an additional co-organizer. Resources produced by the hackathon have already had a significant impact on the research of several scholars (P. Wainwright, pers. comm.). The hackathons have been extraordinarily successful as judged by the participants, and we continue to seek timely and important software development goals around which to organize future events. As one user commented in an anonymous survey

following the most recent hackathons, “the research benefits for the community and for my own work significantly outstripped my expectations.”

In addition to the physical hackathon events, which do not provide an effective means for participants to collaborate on an ongoing basis, we have begun working with the Croquet Consortium (<http://www.opencroquet.org/>), based at Duke University, to experiment with the use of virtual world technology for remote scientific collaborations. One potential benefit of collaboration through virtual worlds is that some barriers to participation in informatics activities by members of under-represented groups may be lowered.

C. Education: The evolutionary biology community, K-16 and the public NESCent supports a unique postdoctoral community.

Our most fundamental training activity is the **NESCent postdoctoral position**. NESCent has created a new model for training in evolutionary biology. Here 13-15 postdoctoral fellows with diverse interests work side-by-side with sabbatical scholars and a host of local faculty. These postdoctoral fellows are provided numerous opportunities to interact with hundreds of visiting scientists in any given year. The breadth of exposure to evolutionary biology is unmatched. The in-house community currently includes 13 postdoctoral fellows, 2 sabbatical scholars, 2 Triangle scholars, and several visiting scientists. This community has a regular seminar series, at least one new in-house working group, a professional development series for postdocs, a journal club, active intranet communications, a Darwin Day scientific symposium, and a host of social traditions. Many of the NESCent fellows and scholars interact regularly with scientists at the three host institutions.

A distinctive feature of this community is its disciplinary diversity. Unlike the research lab environment of a typical postdoc, postdocs and faculty at NESCent come from a variety of different disciplines and backgrounds, and address a diversity of evolutionary questions. The commonalities of this scientific community are the perspectives and tools for synthetic research. Relational databases; meta-analyses; informatics tools for data-mining, data assembly, and visualization; new methods for phylogenetic, genetic, phenotypic and comparative analysis—these are common themes in the in-house community, providing a dynamic environment for interaction and collaboration, and essential training for this next generation of modern evolutionary biologists.

We have seen our first cohort of postdoctoral fellows leave NESCent this past year. Two have moved on to further postdoctoral positions (including a NSF Minority Research Fellowship) and three have accepted tenure track faculty positions (University of Oregon, Mississippi State University, University of Missouri, St. Louis). Several more are currently interviewing for tenure track positions.

NESCent is helping to train the next generation of synthetic researchers.

Our experience in organizing the hackathons taught us the need to involve younger software-savvy evolutionary biologists so that they will be in a position to contribute to open development software projects in the future. We also learned how rare it is to find females among the ranks of academic software developers. We responded by offering a **Phyloinformatics Summer Course** geared to computationally advanced students (including postdocs and young faculty, http://www.nescent.org/summer_course), and, through targeted recruitment, successfully

achieved a nearly equal sex ratio among the participants (11/23). We also organized scientists from throughout the evolutionary biology software community to serve as mentors in the **Google Summer of Code** (<http://code.google.com/soc>), and remotely sponsored 11 undergraduate and graduate summer interns (2 female) through this extremely rewarding program. We expect to continue both these programs in the summer of 2008.

In the future NESCent will host a small, rotating roster of summer courses on different topics. One currently in the planning stages (with Dr. Jessica Gurevitch of SUNY Stony Brook) is on the topic of meta-analysis. We also regularly provide financial assistance and staff support, when appropriate, to other summer courses, such as the **Analytic Paleontology Summer Course** (<http://www.palass.org/modules.php?name=palaeo&sec=careers&page=165>) and the **Bodega Bay Phylogenetics Workshop** (<http://www.nescent.org/news/thisweek.php?id=58>). We have specifically targeted our funds toward travel scholarships for women and underrepresented groups in evolutionary biology.

NESCent is promoting collaborative solutions for effective K-16 evolution education.

The Center has sponsored working groups that bring biology educators together to examine key issues, develop novel approaches in curriculum development, and promote participation across institutions, levels, and student backgrounds. For example, the “**Evolution across the Curriculum**” working group focuses on the high school and undergraduate level. This group is developing exemplars and discussing strategies that will allow instructors to thread evolution comprehensively throughout the biology curriculum. The “**Tree Reasoning in Evolution Education (TREE)**” working group focuses attention on common misunderstandings associated with the use and interpretation of phylogenies, develops strategies for monitoring student understanding of diagrams and figures used to explain evolutionary history, and coordinates efforts to assess teaching strategies in comparative biology. The “**SELECTION**” working group is developing laboratory modules based on real scientific data that can be used in biology curricula at various educational levels.

Targeted Sabbatical Scholar Joe Fail, a faculty member at Johnson C. Smith University in Charlotte, NC, developed a **new biology curriculum for elementary school students**. This curriculum assumed two things: first, that elementary school students are capable of high level science, including inquiry based learning; and second, that evolution should be integrated across the entire curriculum. Fail is currently looking for a publisher for a book based on this curriculum. NESCent, in collaboration with the NC School of Science and Math, held a week long workshop for elementary school teachers to work with Fail on this curriculum in the summer of 2007. The course was a tremendous success, with 16 teachers from various schools around the state participating. Of particular note is the fact that these teachers generally came from school districts with high (32-94%) minority populations. With funds from Duke University we intend to offer this workshop again in 2008.

NESCent is a resource center for information on evolutionary biology for educators.

The NESCent Education and Outreach Group is working to develop and distribute up-to-date, informative, and compelling multimedia resources for biology teachers and students on subject matter drawn from diverse areas of evolutionary biology. A goal is to provide resource materials that can be rapidly incorporated into existing lesson plans and curricula and provide subject matter drawn from various levels of scientific research to give a real-time view of the impact and importance of evolutionary principles in understanding biological phenomena. These products

draw on the confluence of ideas, talents, and enthusiasm brought to the Center by the full breadth of participants in NESCent activities.

In collaboration with AIBS, NESCent organizes and co-sponsors a day-long **symposium on Evolution at the National Association of Biology Teachers (NABT)** annual conference. In support of the symposium topic, NESCent EOG staff and Center scientists have produced an instructional CD-ROM that is distributed widely, at no cost, at NABT and other meetings and workshops. The CD content is also available on the NESCent website (<http://www.nescent.org/media/nabt2007/index.html>). The CD contains teaching resources such as curriculum materials, film clips, activities, and weblinks, as well as biographical information on symposium speakers. Topics have included “Macroevolution” in 2006, and “Evolution and Human Health” in 2007. Development is underway on an “Illuminating Biology through Evolution” CD for 2008. Additionally, we have begun recording presentations of general interest, such as the NABT symposium, and posting these on our website for educators to use in class.

Another way that NESCent is reaching the broader educational community is through our **“Evolution in the News” and podcasting initiatives**. “Evolution in the News” is a series of articles for teachers and students about current events in evolutionary biology. The stories include an overview of the research, and links to media coverage and educational resources. We have initiated a partnership with UC Berkeley’s “Understanding Evolution” (Judy Scotchmoor, <http://evolution.berkeley.edu/>) website to work together to develop and broadcast these pieces. The podcast program is a multimedia enhancement of the stories, providing resources for different learning styles, incorporating graduate student “reporters” and highlighting breaking discoveries and exciting research programs. Our podcast rubric has also been used as an exercise for undergraduate biology majors in a course at UNC who are asked to research and produce their own evolution podcast.

D. Partnering with the broader community

NESCent promotes science in the local community.

Although NESCent is a national organization, several of our activities have had a significant impact on the local community. Through these activities, we reach a large number of individuals underrepresented in evolutionary biology because of the demographic diversity of our area. Our local efforts have almost entirely been financed by funds from Duke University, and bring significant additional attention to the Center.

A noteworthy community event is our annual **Darwin Day celebration**. In 2007 it was a relatively small affair, but in 2008 the symposium was a major Triangle event. We invited 6 speakers on **“Origins and Early Evolution of Life.”** The symposium was held at the national headquarters for **Sigma Xi in the Research Triangle Park**. Several goals were simultaneously achieved. The symposium topics and speakers were largely planned by a committee of postdocs. Many associated activities of the symposium were organized to maximize postdoctoral fellow interaction with the invited speakers. It brought a number of outstanding scientists to the Center, many in fields that are not central areas of evolutionary biology (philosophy, astrobiology, geology, cell biology). At least two new collaborations were spawned during this period, and two invited speakers have already inquired about the possibility of further activities at the Center. Finally it was a tremendous public success with over 200 registrants. Attendees were from many colleges, high schools and universities around

the state, and we had several groups from traditionally minority serving institutions. The Center provided funds for travel for a class from Johnson C. Smith University, a minority serving institution in Charlotte, NC. In addition, there was wide public attendance of individuals from local businesses, government agencies as well as the general public.

NESCent is partnering with the Raleigh Museum of Life Science and Sigma Xi to sponsor “**Science Cafés**” on the topic of evolution. The “Science Café” movement is a way to bring active scientists into the community to interact with the public in a comfortable, non-threatening environment.

NESCent partners with other organizations to advance major scientific initiatives.

NESCent has taken a leadership role on multiple fronts within the area of informatics for evolutionary biology. Our approach has been to leverage our own modest resources by forging effective partnerships with national and international organizations. For instance, we have partnered with the Generic Model Organism Project as mentioned previously; the Open Bioinformatics Foundation played an important role in promoting our first Hackathon; and the Dryad project is a joint effort involving multiple scientific societies, multiple commercial journals, multiple databases/data centers, an academic information science research center and a university library. Through a partnership with the multi-million dollar **Encyclopedia of Life** project, NESCent is co-organizing a session on “Using the Tree of Life to navigate the Encyclopedia of Life” at the Assembling a Tree of Life PI meeting in New Orleans in March.

Another productive partnership is with the National Center for Biomedical Ontologies, or NCBO. One of the first projects sponsored by the Center was a working group organized by Paula Mabee and Monte Westerfield entitled “**Towards an integrated database for fish evolution.**” This group sought to apply phenotype ontologies to catalog natural morphological variation among the large clade of Cypriniform fishes. This was done to enable a database system that could simultaneously query the large dataset of naturally occurring phenotypic variation among species and the equally large collection of developmental data from genetic mutants in the model organism zebrafish. The working group culminated in a successful grant proposal to NSF, through which NESCent has actively partnered with the NCBO. As part of this project, known as Phenoscape (www.phenoscape.org), NESCent is both using, and making major contributions to NCBO software (particularly Phenote, www.phenote.org/) and ontologies (e.g., the Phenotype and Trait Ontology, standards for multispecies anatomical ontologies, standards for taxonomic ontologies, evidence codes for curation). NESCent is also helping to educate to the greater evolutionary biology community about the uses of, and resources for working with, ontologies through annual workshops. NESCent and NCBO are cosponsoring a day-long workshop on the application of phenotype ontologies immediately prior to the Evolution Meetings in Minneapolis in June of 2008. A future workshop is being planned for the Society for Integrative and Comparative Biology meetings in 2009.

A fairly comprehensive list of NESCent partnerships was provided in the annual report; this has been updated and is included here in Appendix 2. This list supports the idea that NESCent has become an important node in a broad network of scientific, informatic and educational efforts nationally and internationally.

PART 2 SOME FACTS AND FIGURES

A. The nature of NESCent science

Because there is an evolutionary perspective on every aspect of biology, encouraging and supporting activities that promote evolutionary analysis and synthesis in all areas of biology is vital to NESCent's mission. In part in response to questions about the breadth of science funded by NESCent raised by the year 2 site visit team, we examined the areas covered by NESCent funded science, and used this to assess our portfolio of activities. Each award or project to date (through Feb 2008) was classified in terms of both a primary and a secondary subject area; the 14 different subject areas represent different levels of biological organization. Table 1 summarizes funded projects in terms of the two subject areas.

Primary or Secondary Subject	All Types	Catalysis	Working Group	Post-doc	Sabbatical	Triangle Fellow	Triangle Work Group
Genomics/Proteomics	20	5	5	4	2	4	0
Molecular evolution	14	3	2	4	2	1	2
Development	7	0	4	1	0	2	0
Physiology/Functional Morphology	9	1	2	3	3	0	0
Behavior/Neurobiology	7	1	2	4	0	0	0
Medicine	3	2	1	0	0	0	0
Evolutionary Ecology & Population Biology	21	1	5	8	5	2	0
Evolutionary Genetics	19	3	3	2	7	3	1
Phylogeography & Speciation	9	2	2	3	2	0	0
Conservation	2	1	1	0	0	0	0
Comparative Biology	19	4	3	11	0	1	0
Systematics & Phylogenetics	14	2	7	2	3	0	0
Paleontology	11	1	3	5	0	1	1
Education	5	0	2	0	3	0	0

Table 1: primary and secondary fields represented by NESCent funded projects.

These data demonstrate that collectively our funded activities address a diversity of fundamental evolutionary questions in evolution, systematics and comparative biology and cover nearly all important areas of evolutionary biology. Areas that are well-represented at NESCent, both in our in-house community and visiting meetings and working groups, include genomics and molecular evolution, evolutionary ecology and evolutionary genetics, and systematic and comparative biology. Other areas such as development and behavior/neurobiology are more poorly represented. Obviously not all areas are equally represented by each class of participant (postdocs and working groups, for example), but on the whole the breadth of evolutionary

biology is well represented by our programs. Our Senior Advisory Board evaluated this issue at their August 2007 meeting, and concluded that that NESCent is doing an excellent job of supporting a diversity of scientific projects.

Another important aspect is the intrinsic interdisciplinary nature of NESCent activities. Many major scientific challenges require the integration of perspectives and tools from multiple disciplines. NESCent's emphasis on cross-disciplinary research brings together groups of scientists who might otherwise not talk to one another and provides a supportive and effective environment for stimulating synthetic research, individually and in collaboration. NESCent breaks down inter-institutional barriers to collaboration, and provides an opportunity for evolutionary biologists with radically different expertise to work together.

While our catalysis meetings were established to promote this integration across disciplines, we see such interdisciplinary activities in all our programs. Our group of in-house scientists is inherently interdisciplinary, and many working groups likewise contain individuals from different traditional fields and approaches. Indeed the majority of projects at NESCent involve interdisciplinary approaches. As one indicator of this, we classify each project in terms of level of organization: molecular, organismal, population, and phylogenetic. The majority of projects can be classified as crossing at least two different levels. A summary of projects funded through February 2008 (Table 2) show that most NESCent projects integrate across at least two levels of organization.

	Molecular	Organism	Population	Phylogeny
Molecular	4	5	8	8
Organism		2	7	8
Population			10	10
Phylogeny				9

Table 2: levels of organization of study in NESCent funded projects

This summary demonstrates that our scientific research portfolio includes a wide range of approaches and biological levels of organization within evolutionary biology and associated fields. The complete listing of NESCent scientific projects funded through year 3 is provided in Appendix 1.

B. Outcomes

The first scientific activities by NESCent began in late summer and fall of 2005, just over 2.5 years ago. Many of the products of these activities are still ongoing, but we can clearly document the success of NESCent-supported research, based on the reports by NESCent participants through mid-February 2008 (Table 3). Thus far, these activities have resulted in 70 publications, 13 grant awards, 21 software or database products, and many new collaborations. Working groups, sabbatical scholars and postdoctoral fellows are all contributing importantly to this total. Increasingly, catalysis meetings are contributing to new collaborations and collaborative grant proposals. Hosted meetings and other activities have also contributed to

NESCent productivity. We will continue to document this productivity, and begin to assess the impacts of these products in the coming years.

Products	Postdoc	Sabbatical scholars	Working Groups	Catalysis Meetings	Other	Totals
Publications	11(6)	33(4)	18(11)	2(2)	6(4)	70(27)
Grants/Proposals	3(2)	3	3(1)	2(7)	2(4)	13(14)
Software	8	1	3(1)	0	9	21(1)
Collaborations	14	5	4	6	10	39

Table 3: products arising from NESCent sponsored projects (as of February, 2008); numbers in parentheses represent products submitted or in preparation

C. Demographics of NESCent supported activities

Appendix 3 contains specific information on the demographics of our applicant pool and funded scientists. Key points to take away from these data are:

Gender: Approximately 25% of funded scholars and meeting PIs are female, while somewhat fewer than 25% of applicants in these categories are female. Our postdoc applicants are approximately 40% female and ~ 43% of our postdoctoral awards have been to females.

Race and ethnic groups: We have received few applicants from African-American and Hispanic scientists, and none from self-identified Native Americans. We have funded members of these groups at a disproportionately high level.

Citizenship: The majority of our applicants and the majority of our funded scientists are US Citizens and are residents of the US.

Residency of participants: We have had participants in our funded activities from 25 non-US countries, including several from the developing world. We have had funded participants from all but 7 states as well as the District of Columbia (see Appendix 4).

D. External grants

In order to accomplish its broader mission, NESCent must obtain funding beyond the core grant. Thus far NESCent has been successful in application for funding for several of its informatics initiatives including the GMOD project and a major collaborative project (phenote; see below) that grew out of a working group. We have 4 proposals pending or in preparation, including funding for Dryad, our digital data repository for evolutionary biology. Details of these proposals are provided in Appendix 5.

E. NESCent activities towards the recruitment of underserved groups

The effort to further recruit underrepresented groups into evolutionary biology is a core commitment of the Center and is integrated into EOG, Science, and Informatics activities. A fuller discussion of activities is presented in Appendix 6; briefly, they include:

- Active consideration and recruitment of applicants from underrepresented groups in our science programs.
- A “targeted” sabbatical program, which is focused on bringing faculty members from Minority Serving Institutions (MSIs) to NESCent.
- A program of undergraduate research internships.
- Particular recruitment and scholarship efforts to bring individuals from underrepresented groups to our summer informatics courses.
- Activities that include teachers and students from local schools.
- Sponsorship of a working group composed of evolutionary biologists from minority serving institutions - Evolution Education at Historically Minority Universities (EEHMU).
- Arranging invited speakers from NESCent for classes at MSIs.
- Development with Scott Edwards of a program to recruit and provide scholarships for faculty and promising undergraduate students from MSIs to attend the annual meeting of the Society for the Study of Evolution.
- Sponsorship of an impressive set of programs for the SACNAS (Society for the Advancement of Chicanos and Native Americans in Science) meeting.
- Recruitment and payment of travel expenses for classes from MSIs to attend our Darwin Day symposium.
- Making scientific and educational material more easily accessible to underrepresented groups, through efforts such as our Evolution in the news podcast program and our education working groups.
- Assembly and maintenance of databases to allow students to locate graduate programs in evolution, and graduate recruiters to identify undergraduate programs at minority serving institutions.
- Targeted recruitment of faculty from MSIs for the SELECTION workshop.

F. Operations and administration

Organizational structure

NESCent’s Directors: NESCent’s current leadership is composed of a Center Director and three Associate Directors (see organizational chart in Appendix 7). Each Associate Director provides leadership for one of NESCent’s branches and also ensures that the three universities are represented in NESCent’s overall management. The Center Director works closely with each branch to coordinate these activities, provides overall leadership for Center activities, represents NESCent nationally, oversees NESCent administration, and works with Duke’s administration

and NSF. Although there has been significant turnover in leadership in NESCent's short life (most recently in the position of Associate Director for EOG and therefore representation from North Carolina State University), the current team works extremely well together. Despite the fact that the three branches have somewhat different points of emphasis and responsibility they increasingly overlap in fulfilling NESCent's mission. Informatics and synthetic science are often inextricably intertwined; certain outreach activities are central to all activities of the Center; several of our working groups and "science" activities are devoted to the enhancement of understanding, communicating and teaching evolutionary biology.

Operations committee: Major decisions regarding NESCent's operation and direction are made in consultation with an Operations Committee. This committee is composed of the four Directors as well as an at large member from each of the three participating institutions and one postdoctoral fellow (selected by the postdoctoral fellows). The operations committee approves recommendations for funding from the Scientific Advisory Board, reviews postdocs for second and third years of funding, discusses all major Center initiatives, and reviews various reports to be provided to advisory boards and NSF. Members of the Operations Committee serve as informal mentors to postdoctoral fellows, and as possible, interact with in-house scientists. The terms of the members are 1.5 – 2 years; all current members have agreed to serve through the site visit and renewal application. New members are nominated by the current Operations Committee.

In addition to their service as members of the Operations Committee, faculty members from local institutions participate in Center activities in a number of ways. Some serve as advisors and collaborators for our postdocs, others are resident at the Center for a semester or longer as Triangle Sabbatical Scholars, and many participate in scientific meetings and seminars.

Recruitment plan for new Director

Currently the Center Director is approximately 50% effort. However there is clear consensus that the Center would benefit from a full time Director. One of the most important additional roles that a full time Center Director may play is national outreach to further extend the reach of the Center to fields beyond the core evolutionary biology community.

Duke University has agreed to recruit a full time Director for the Center if it is renewed for a second 5 year award. Depending on the results of the site visit, a search committee will be formed in the summer of 2008, and a search commence in the fall of 2008. The search committee will be run out of the office of the Dean for Natural Science at Duke University, and will likely be composed of faculty members from Duke University as well as UNC and NCSU, members of our Senior Advisory Board, and others to be determined.

Advisory Boards

NESCent has two advisory boards (confusingly both are abbreviated SAB). The **Senior Advisory Board** is composed of national and international leaders in evolutionary biology. This group meets yearly to discuss NESCent's overall direction and effectiveness. It provides critical feedback to the Directors on our programs and progress. Our hope is that it also serves as NESCent's advocate and representative nationally. In addition to yearly meetings, the Director communicates with this group or its Chair several times a year, often soliciting advice on specific issues. Barbara Schaal was Chair for years 1 & 2; David Hillis is currently Chair. Members serve rotating three year terms. Current membership of this Board may be found on our website (http://www.nescent.org/dir/advise_board.php).

The **Science Advisory Board** meets twice a year and is composed of a variety of scientists who provide evaluation and recommendation on proposals for funding. The Science Advisory Board also discusses general issues of NESCent science, including the number and diversity of applications and the strengths and weaknesses of our various programs. This group is chaired by Joel Kingsolver. Members serve rotating three year terms. Current membership of this Board may be found on our website (http://www.nescent.org/dir/science_board.php).

Shortly after the year 2 reorganization an **Informatics Advisory Board** was formed. This group was intended to provide informal advice on major cyberinfrastructure initiatives. However, as we added more informatics expertise to our other advisory boards, we realized that a separate board was not necessary. With the advice and support of our Senior Advisory Board in August 2007 we disbanded this group as a formal board.

Institutional Support

Thus far, direct institutional support has been largely limited to Duke University. Duke University provided funds for the renovation and furnishing of the physical Center, and currently provides \$186,000 in direct support to the Center each year (\$66,000 for Center rent, and \$120,000 for a Director's discretionary fund) and more than \$100,000 in support of the Director annually (teaching replacement, laboratory support and summer salary) in addition to her full 9 month salary. Additionally Duke has allowed the Center an off-campus overhead rate. UNC has provided overhead reductions; however, release time and summer compensation for Associate Directors Kingsolver and Vision are currently charged directly to the grant. North Carolina State University has not provided a reduced overhead rate, however, all the time of Associate Director Wiegmann is provided by NCSU. We are currently in negotiation with both UNC and NCSU to increase their direct contribution and hope that by the site visit such agreements will be in place.

One important component of regularizing the University support is the drafting of a formal memorandum of understanding. This agreement will be put in place if the grant is renewed. Specific aspects may be modified as a result of the site visit, planning resulting from the renewal application and the Director search; however we anticipate that the following components will be included:

- a) Agreement regarding indirect costs. Depending on the institution this may include some of the following aspects: reduced overhead on the core grant, a process of overhead return directly to the Center, and/or special agreements regarding grants beyond the core grant.
- b) "Master agreement". The three Universities will agree that the budgeting for certain kinds of activities can be transferred among Universities without major re-writing of subcontracts. These might include funding of meetings and other activities, support of students or staff salary. We will put in place a process of "task orders" for transfer of effort among the Universities.
- c) Universities will agree to support the Directors and Associate Directors in a manner that is appropriate to their job requirements. The specifics will be worked out by individual Universities; this will be an agreement in principle.
- d) Universities will agree to develop means to increase interaction among faculty and students in their department and NESCent. Include developing mechanism for mini faculty leaves to encourage the Triangle sabbatical program.

PART 3 LOOKING FORWARD

Although we believe NESCent has substantially met most of the major goals set for the Center in the original proposal, the Center will continue to grow in scope and impact as we look forward. There are areas in which we have not yet reached our potential and others that deserve serious consideration for further development. In this section we discuss these issues, some of which were raised in the year 2 site visit. Further we raise a number of fundamental questions for consideration. Many of these questions are “strategic” in the sense that the answer will result in decisions about differential allocation of resources (both time and money) and in some cases significant changes to our focus. We believe consideration of these questions is important to the future of the Center, and would value the site visit team’s opinion as appropriate.

A. Evaluating our transformative impact.

The greatest challenge to a center such as ours which aims to “change the culture of collaboration” or “transform the nature of evolutionary biology” is the assessment of our impact. We can list the productivity of our science and gather testimonials on how NESCent support has had a substantial impact on individual scientists, but this is not sufficient. In the coming year we will explore methods to evaluate the broader impacts of large scale activities such as NESCent. We expect that establishing such an evaluation plan will include setting new questions, collecting new data and establishing new analytical approaches, and intend to converse with many individuals on potential approaches. For example, we have initiated discussions with the Carolina Population Center at UNC, to explore methods to quantify the patterns and effectiveness of collaborative research at interdisciplinary research centers like NESCent and the CPC. We have invited Dr. Katy Börner (<http://ella.slis.indiana.edu/~katy/>), an expert in the study of collaborative scientific networks, to NESCent to discuss a potential approach to examine such questions. We are also in the process of initiating conversations with other individuals, who have also considered ways to understand complex interactions.

Question: Devising mechanisms for such assessments are not easy and may require new and complex ways of thinking about how science is done. However, we assume this approach is increasingly important as NSF funds more and more large-scale, collaborative initiatives. To what extent is NSF willing to help provide a roadmap for the assessment of scientific transformation?

B. Continuing to broaden outreach and impact within and beyond the core evolutionary biology community.

The year 2 site visit recommended broadening our outreach to the evolutionary biology community as there was an impression that we were not serving the entire community. In year 3 we made several advances in our outreach efforts:

- Our redesigned website came on line in January 2007. This website experiences 2000-3000 visits a month; about half of these are from outside the state of North Carolina (which helps us distinguish internal from external traffic; see appendix 8).
- NESCent representatives attended a much wider range of meetings, in many cases manning a booth in the exhibit hall. A complete list of meetings attended in year 3 is provided in appendix 9.

- We advertised our call for proposals widely in major listserves and websites for evolutionary and organismal biology, genomics and informatics (appendix 10).
- K. Smith wrote personal emails to individuals at approximately 40 major universities with strong programs in evolutionary biology outlining the programs and opportunities at NESCent. We requested that these be forwarded broadly to potentially interested postdocs and faculty at each university. These were at least partially effective, as we could document an elevated level of web traffic from targeted cities following the emails.
- We developed a new quarterly newsletter that provides updates on activities, programs, funding opportunities, deadlines and awards. Currently approximately 1200 individuals are on our newsletter list.

As we look to the future we must continue these efforts. There are several activities that will increase our potential scope. First, we believe NESCent-initiated activities, such as our Darwin Day symposium, and Evolution 2020 projects (see below), which bring a wide variety of speakers to the Center, will allow us to target specific fields. Second, we believe a full time Director will have significantly more time for broad outreach activities, and in particular will be better able to achieve the goal of reaching out to non-traditional communities. Finally, as we become better known within the evolutionary biology community, news of NESCent will naturally spread.

Question: Fundamental questions remain on how NESCent should balance its services and resources in supporting our core evolutionary biology community versus trying to recruit other fields to evolutionary biology. Such fields include physical sciences, such as chemistry; applied fields in biology such as agriculture, medicine and conservation biology; or social and cultural sciences, such as cultural anthropology, linguistics or philosophy. To what extent should NESCent focus on engaging a broader community and what groups are of particular interest?

C. Attracting applicants, particularly postdocs, from a diverse pool.

As most NESCent activities are, and should be, investigator initiated our most important path to a broad and diverse scientific community is through our applicant pool. In our year 2 site visit report several questions were raised about the scientific breadth of our supported science. While, as discussed above, we feel that some of these issues were overstated, we did make several changes to our advertisement and application evaluation process. In particular, in response to questions about the postdoctoral program we:

- Now provide more detailed information about the postdoctoral program on the website, including extensive descriptions about the opportunities unique to NESCent.
- Made clear that collaborations and limited empirical research projects are permitted.
- Strengthened our local mentoring program.
- Slightly modified our evaluation process so that greater emphasis was placed on overall ability (as measured by productivity and letters of recommendation) rather than simply project description.

We believe our most recent cohort of awardees is very strong, scientifically broad and demographically diverse. Awardees are being notified as this is written so we can't confirm who will accept our offers, but our top postdoc candidates are proposing topics such as gene duplication and evolutionary developmental biology, social behavior and disease transmission,

gene expression and evolutionary patterns, phylogenetic and ecological modeling, social behavior and neurobiology, macroevolutionary patterns in the fossil record, patterns of island extinction, and models of inbreeding and dispersal.

In our efforts to continue to recruit applicants from underrepresented groups we pursue both short- and long-term strategies. Our short-term strategies include participating in efforts to recruit members from under-represented groups into evolutionary biology through our workshops at the SACNAS meeting and our Evolution meeting scholarships, convening professional development sessions focusing on minority issues, direct recruiting through our partnerships at MSIs and the EEHMu group, continual recruitment efforts and financial support to members of underrepresented groups to attend our informatics training programs. In the long run we will continue to cultivate our relationships with faculty and students at MSIs to help build a pipeline for applicants to all of our programs.

Question: NESCent has made significant efforts to include members of under-represented groups in our activities, for example by ensuring that members of such groups are on our advisory panels, are funded when possible when applying for NESCent support, and are recruited into courses we offer. Further we participate in a large number of outreach activities. To a large extent the issue is a significant “pipeline” problem. There simply are not large numbers of candidates for funding from some groups. What are NSF and the community’s expectations for, and acceptable measures of success in, this area for NESCent?

D. Maintaining a continuously vibrant community of sabbatical scholars & bringing a diverse array of scientists to the Center.

While we have had a number of sabbatical scholars that have had an extraordinary impact on the Center, have been highly productive, and have served as wonderful mentors for our postdocs, we realize our sabbatical program has had uneven success. We feel that part of this may be due to the fact that the traditional sabbatical model (where a faculty member moves for a year to another institution) is increasingly impractical for many; we have been told that NCEAS is facing similar issues. Nonetheless we see a sustained program of bringing visiting scientists to the Center for extended periods as a critical part of our in-house program. In order to enhance this program we have initiated or considered a number of activities:

- We have initiated a program of short term visitors. This program supports visitors to come to NESCent for several weeks to several months. We particularly encourage collaborative ventures, so that two or three investigators come simultaneously. Applications are open 4 times a year and we promise fast turn around. Thus far we have funded 5 such visitors.
- We have initiated a Distinguished Scholar program. This program is targeted towards senior scientists with whom we hope to work to convert rich legacy data sets into digital forms for deposition into the Dryad repository.
- We have expanded our support for the sabbatical scholars, increasing the stipend slightly, and providing a bit more flexibility in funding.
- We have discussed establishing a number of alternative programs. These include a program modeled after the themed workshops hosted by the Isaac Newton Institute for Applied Mathematics at the University of Cambridge. There, scientists apply to organize research themes by inviting a group of long-term visitors who will interact intensively over the course of a semester.

- We have discussed establishing some form of “honorary programs” (named lectureships; best young investigator, etc.), which would be a way of attracting attention and visits of more senior scientists to the Center.
- We have provided additional funding to working groups. In some cases this funding has been used by working group organizers to bring small subsets of the members of the group to NESCent for short visits.
- As a part of other efforts such as our Evolution 2020 initiative, we will bring senior scientists to the Center for shorter visits and encourage them to consider the Center for longer projects.

Other possible initiatives include greater effort towards targeted recruitment and further increasing the attractiveness of the award (more flexibility, more funding, greater support to maintain ties to existing lab with stipends to bring students or postdocs to NESCent for short periods, etc.).

Question: In what ways can we foster a sabbatical/visiting scientist program that will be highly attractive and bring the very best senior evolutionary biologists to the Center? Should we focus on ways to bring senior scientists to the Center by invitation, or should we continue to largely be responsive to investigator initiated programs? Should we expand our “targeted” program, which currently focuses on individuals from primarily minority serving institutions? The previous site visit suggested that NESCent sponsor a large number of events which would bring invited senior scientists to the Center. In addition to being logistically difficult, this kind of program would require a significant redirection of funds. Is it an appropriate redirection?

E. Continually obtaining broad community input.

NESCent has in large measure responded to applications from the scientific community as the major focus for its funded activities. At the same time we have been in continual conversations with various constituencies about what potential areas might be particularly fruitful, and what new approaches might make an impact. Such conversations have included:

- The “Wilmington meeting,” which was held at the very start of NESCent’s funding, and brought together a large number of scientists to discuss the most important issues in the field. The results of this meeting had significant effect on determining the directions for our major cyberinfrastructure initiatives such as GMOD and DRYAD.
- We regularly discuss new areas and new initiatives with both our advisory boards. These discussions have helped us focus our attention on potential new areas. In particular these discussions have helped us identify areas that are significantly under-represented in our sponsored science.
- We have an open “white paper” program, particularly for informatics. In this program, any member of the community can propose to us a potential new initiative. One notable success of the white paper program was our “comparative methods in R” hackathons. However, we would like to see this program more widely used.
- The Directors regularly discuss options with other scientists at meetings and other venues. Many of our partnerships, which represent important new synthetic activities, have arisen through this mechanism.

- We selectively encourage certain inquiries into funding opportunities from under-represented areas, and in some cases provide detailed feedback on applications.

We anticipate expanding our efforts for community input as we prepare a renewal grant for a second five years of funding. Such efforts would include a variety of targeted conversations, discussions with our advisory boards, and the probable organization of a community summit entitled “Re-envisioning NESCent.”

F. NESCent initiated programs and activities.

Although the year 2 site visit team suggested a wide range of NESCent initiated activities, we believe that we must be careful to maintain a balance between activities that we initiate (and fund), versus those that are initiated by the wider community. We do not believe it is our mission to spend large parts of the core grant on activities initiated by Center Directors. Nonetheless we realize that carefully targeted activities can serve multiple purposes and are worth the investment of time and money. We have already discussed our Darwin Day activities, and noted how they served many functions. We believe a small number of symposia and workshops can bring attention to the Center and can catalyze important new insight. Further, activities such as hackathons have had an enormous impact and we will continue to organize such events.

One program we are in the process of organizing is “Evolution 2020.” This program was enthusiastically endorsed by our Senior Advisory Board, and consists of inviting a number of senior scientists, either individually, or in groups to write brief commentaries on where research in evolutionary biology will be leading us in the next decade. Many of these commentaries will be the result of short workshops held at the Center. This will be a multi-year effort, surrounding the 200th anniversary of Darwin’s birthday. We have a very positive response from *PLoS Biology* as a potential publisher of this series. This project will serve a number of functions, including bringing further attention to NESCent, allowing us to extend our reach beyond the immediate evolutionary biology community, and in many cases bringing scientists to the Center for short symposia and workshops.

Question: To what extent should NESCent initiate activities to be funded from our core grant? In our first 2.5 years of funding we were actively discouraged by NSF program officers from funding activities that were generated internally, rather than from the community. This extended to both science activities and informatics initiatives. More recently, there have been increased suggestions that NESCent should proactively identify areas ripe for synthesis and begin undertaking activities that will bring attention to the Center. To what extent should we initiate the activities that we fund, and to what extent should we primarily respond to the interests of our community?

G. Administrative issues.

Several issues regarding Center administration require further consideration as we look forward. These issues include:

Advisory boards. We currently have two excellent advisory boards. These boards serve slightly different functions, but serve us well. As we face our renewal, we will discuss with each

Board its changing mission as NESCent itself changes, and seek to define the best possible composition and mission of each.

Directors and representations from the universities. In the long run we see a similar structure (Director and Associate Directors) continuing, although it is possible that in the course of the next five years that there may be further personnel change. We do not believe that the current specific structure necessarily needs to be retained in the future. For example, with a full-time Director some aspects of oversight of one or another of the branches might migrate centrally; the number of Associate Directors from each institution might change; with changing personnel, the specific areas of oversight might move from one institution to another; alternatively, new responsibilities might be defined given the specific interests of newly recruited Associate Directors.

Institutional support. In the early years institutional support was somewhat uneven. We are working with UNC Chapel Hill and North Carolina State University to increase their direct support of the Center. We are also developing a formal Memorandum of Understanding to be signed by all three Universities. We need to devise ways to shift funds across the subcontracts as the current system often introduces significant awkwardness and unnecessary difficulty in funding our projects.

Staffing. NESCent has an excellent staff (see organizational chart in appendix 7); however, in some ways we are pushed to the limits. As the number of yearly Center visitors has stabilized at around 700, our logistics and financial staff members' jobs have expanded. Further as the range of informatics initiatives and partnerships increase, oversight of both supported science and major initiatives becomes particularly difficult to manage. We have thus far met additional staffing needs through external funding, and in some cases, contributions from Duke University. In our long range planning, we must carefully evaluate our staff needs to determine if they are currently at the proper level.

Funding issues. We see one of the greatest challenges of the second five years the expansion of the base of the Center. While we have had significant success in gaining external funding during the first 3 years, the long term health of the Center will depend on broadening the scope of the Center's funding. We believe this is one of the major tasks of a new full time Director.

H. Looking forward.

We are enthusiastic about the chance to continue to develop NESCent over the next 5 years. We believe it is important to remember that NESCent as an organization has existed just over 3 years, and has occupied its space for just over 2 years. In this time, we have brought over 1600 scientists together in one forum or another, supported a variety of unique interactions through our catalysis and working groups, and facilitated the production of a large number of publications, software packages and other output. We have meaningful partnerships with organizations of all levels in all areas throughout the world and we have applied for and received significant grant funds beyond the core grant. However, NESCent is still in its early stages and there is tremendous potential yet to be realized. This is an exciting time.

Appendix 1, Visitors to NESCent Years 1-3

	# of Visitors and number of meetings					
Year	Science	Education	Informatics	Advisory	Hosted	Total
1 visitors	85	15	0	28	138	266
1 meetings	4	2	0	3	1	10
2 visitors	288	13	16	37	184	538
2 meetings	13	2	1	3	4	23
3 visitors	452	98	62	23	180	815
3 meetings	30	5	1	2	16	54

Visitors to the Center in years 1-3. Science includes all meetings sponsored (or co-sponsored by NESCent); informatics includes meetings such as hackathons and the digital data workshop; education includes courses in which students are brought to the Center for training, and includes the phyloinformatics course, for example; advisory meetings are meetings of our advisory boards; hosted are meetings by various groups that NESCent hosts, but does not provide financial support. Each annual report details the meetings and participants for that year.

List of NESCent Funded Activities Years 1-3

Postdoctoral Fellows

Year 1

- The Phylogenetics of Desiccation Tolerance in the Land Plants - Kirsten Fisher
- Comparative Genomic Studies of the Sequences Responsible for the Regulation of Gene Expression - Joshua Granek
- Numt Variation in Metazoan Genomes: Gain, Loss, Duplication and Possible Function - Einat Hazkani-Covo
- Adaptive Divergence Between Natural Populations - Joe Hereford
- Phylogeographical Information Science: Linking Phylogenies and Earth History - David Kidd
- Cetartiodactyl Evolution: Understanding the Evolutionary Transition from the Terrestrial to the Biome - Samantha Price
- Hydraulic Efficiency and Safety: Do Tradeoffs Have an Evolutionary Basis in the Rosids? - Amy Zanne
- Implementation of a Wide Range of Condon and Amino Acid Models in Bayesian Phylogenetic Software - Derrick Zwickl

Year 2

- A Phylogenetic Database for Comparative Biology in Land Plants - Gordon Burleigh
- New DCM Methods for Maximum Likelihood, and Pattern Identification in Biogeography - Ganeshkumar Ganapathy
- What is the Relative Importance of Biotic vs. Abiotic Local Adaptation? - Ganeshkumar Ganapathy
- The Evolution of Mammalian Fossoriality: Causes and Consequences - Samantha Hopkins
- Building a Framework for the Study of Cultural Evolution - Lauren McCall
- Understanding Parallel Morphological Diversification in Sister Fish Faunas - Brian Sidlauskas

Year 3

- Methods to Examine Trait Evolution on Trees: Advancing the Field - Brian O'Meara
- Competition and Meso-Evolutionary Change in the Mammalian Fossil Record - Paula Spaeth

Sabbatical Scholars

Year 1

- Attracting Minority Graduate Applicants into Careers in Evolutionary Biology and Developing Research in Molecular Systematics - John Clamp
- Creating an Evolutionary Dataspace for Plants: Allowing Phylogenetic, Morphological and Gene Ontologies to Collide Gracefully - Quentin Cronk
- Estimating the Distribution of Fitness Effects of New Mutations from DNA Sequence Data - Adam Eyre-Walker
- Incorporation of All Maximum Likelihood Phylogenetic Analyses Currently Performed by PAUP*4b10 Into Phycas - Paul Lewis
- Relational Evolutionary Databases for Heliconius Butterflies - Owen McMillan

Year 2

- Chiton Phylogeny and Comparative Phylogeography - Douglas Eernisse
- Designing and Teaching an Evolution Curriculum for Elementary Students - Joseph Fail, Jr.
- A Community Approach to Evolutionary Theory - Sarah Otto
- Evolution in a Spatial Context: A Synthesis of Theory and Review - Michael Whitlock

Year 3

- The Role of Crossing-Over and Recombination in Adaptive Evolution - Malcolm Schug
- Evolution of Performance Curves in Seasonal Environments - George Gilchrist

Short-Term Scholars

Year 3

- Phylogenetic Rate Heterogeneity and Evolution in Filmy Ferns (Hymenophyllaceae) – Sabine Hennequin
- Estimating the Probability of Continuous Character Transitions on Trees – Andrew Hipp and Alexander Platt

Visiting Scholars

Year 1

- Squirrels as Models in Macroevolution; Scaling - Louise Roth (no NESCent funding)
- 1) Software Integration and 2) Permutation Sampling for Genomic Distance – Jijun Tang
- Phylogenetic Systematics and Molecular Evolution in Fungi - Rytas Vilgalys (no NESCent funding)

Year 2

- Comparative Sociobiology and Behavioral Ecology - Clara B. Jones (no NESCent funding)
- Connecting Best Practices Experiences and User Interface Development for Morphological Databases - Martin Ramirez

Triangle Visiting Scholars (no NESCent funding)

Year 1

- Evolutionary Relationships of Devonian Age Fossil Plants – Patricia Gensel
- Analysis of Genetic Data – Spencer Muse
- Genome Evolution and Architecture of Complex Traits, with a Focus on Flowering Plants – Todd Vision
- Evolution of Development and the Molecular Evolution of Transcriptional Regulation - Greg Wray

Year 2

- Analysis of Factors that Determine the Occurrence of Speciation and Reinforcement - Maria Servedio
- Evolutionary Genomics and Bioinformatics of Mimulus, a Developing Model System for Studies of Plant Adaptation and Speciation - John Willis

Year 3

- Phenotypic Plasticity and the Origins of Diversity - David Pfennig
- Evolutionary Genetics and Molecular Evolution - Mark Rausher

Catalysis Meetings

Year 1

- Biological Diversification on the West Indian Archipelago - Rich Glor, Jonathan Losos, Robert Ricklefs
- Integrated Studies of Genetic Networks: A New Evolutionary "Synthesis" - Stephen Proulx, Daniel Promislow, Matthew Hahn
- Behavioral Reconstruction in Paleoanthropology - Daniel Schmitt

Year 2

- Evolution in Contemporary Human Populations: Medical, Genetic and Behavioral Implications - Raju Govindaraju, Peter Byers, Stephen Stearns
- Developing New Model Systems for Evolutionary Genetics and Genomics Using Poeciliid Fishes - Kimberly Hughes, Felix Breden, Detlef Weigel
- Genomic Approaches to the Study of Adaptive Radiation in African Cichlid Fishes - Thomas Kocher
- Historical Perspectives on the Patterns of Biodiversity in Madagascar: Characterization and Applications - Anne Yoder, Claire Kremen
- Selfish DNA and the Genetic Control of Vector-Borne Diseases - Fred Gould, Steven Sinkins, Daniel Hartl
- Origins and Evolution of Chemoreception - Roy Plotnick

Year 3

- Myelin, a New Model for Evolutionary Innovation - Daniel Hartline, David Colman, Petra Hoepcke Lenz, Mark Martindale, Elaine Seaver, Gunter Paul Wagner

Working Groups

Year 1

- Phylogeography of the Northern Hemisphere - Michael Donoghue, Paul Manos
- Understanding the Paradox of Mixed Mating in Flowering Plants - Susan Kalisz, Mark Johnston
- Towards an Integrated Database for Fish Evolution - Paula Mabee, Monte Westerfield

Year 2

- Synergistic Evolutionary LEarning Consortium: Evolution in ACTION - John R. Jungck, Anton E. Weisstein
- The Plant EvoGenomics Working Group: Advancing Comparative Functional Genomics - Jim Leebens-Mack, Eric Brenner
- Proposal to Develop a Novel Journal Concept for Evolutionary Meta-Analyses - Mohamed Noor, Maria R. Servedio
- Fossil and Molecular Estimates of Divergence Times for the Tree of Life: Database and Synthesis - Todd Oakley
- Synthesizing Computational Resources for Cis-Regulatory Molecular Evolution - Casey Bergman, Martin Keitman, Manolis Dermitzakis
- Developing an Integrative Algorithmic Method for Historical Biogeography - Joel Cracraft, Mark Siddall
- Modeling Variation in Gene Networks - Paul Magwene, David Houle
- Phanerozoic Body Size Trends in Time and Space: Macroevolution and Macroecology - Jonathan Payne, Jennifer Stempien, Michael Kowalewski
- Evolutionary Informatics: Supporting Interoperability in Evolutionary Analysis - Arlin Stoltzfus, Rutger Vos
- Evolutionary Ecology of Primate Life Histories - Karen Strier, Susan Alberts

Year 3

- Mechanistic Distribution Models: Energetics, Fitness, and Population Dynamics - Lauren Buckley, Michael Angilletta, Robert Holt, Joshua Tewksbury
- Relaxed Selection and Trait Loss in Evolution - David Lahti, Susan A. Foster
- How Does Cognition Evolve? - Charles Nunn, Brian Hare
- Genetic monitoring: Development of tools for conservation and management (w/ NCEAS) - Michael Schwartz, Fred Allendorf
- Mathematical models, microbes & evolutionary diversification - Samantha Forde, Ivana Gudelj
- Measuring evolutionary change in modern human populations - Diddahal Govindaraju, Andrew Clark, Trudy Mackay, Stephen Stearns
- Montane diversity in space and time - Kenneth Kozak, Catherine Graham, Carsten Rahbek

Triangle Working Groups

Year 2

- Clockwork: Redefining Interfaces for Molecular Biology and Paleontology - Julia Clarke, Nathalie Nagalingum, Brian Wiegmann
- Genomic Patterns and Processes of Introgression - Marcy Uyenoyama, Alade Tokuta, Rasmus Nielsen

APPENDIX 2 CENTER PARTNERSHIPS AND ASSOCIATIONS

NESCent has entered into a diverse array of partnerships during its first three years. These include:

From the start, NESCent has had a strong relationship with NCEAS. The Directors are in frequent contact (and the Director of NCEAS has provided invaluable advice to the NESCent Director), we have jointly funded 3 working groups thus far, and have partnered on data sharing initiatives. NCEAS is also a co-sponsor of our SACNAS activities.

<http://www.nceas.ucsb.edu>

NESCent has collaborated extensively with the Evolutionary Genomics Center (EGC) of Duke's Institute for Genome Science and Policy. The EGC Director, Greg Wray, is a member of our operations committee; the Center jointly sponsored our 2007 Darwin Day symposium on Genomes and Evolution and the EGC is currently working with our EOG group to develop a summer workshop for faculty at primarily teaching institutions

<http://www.genome.duke.edu/centers/ceg>

We are developing a collaboration with the Carolina Population Center at UNC, to explore methods to quantify the patterns and effectiveness of collaborative research at interdisciplinary research centers like NESCent and CPC.

<http://www.cpc.unc.edu/>

NESCent Informatics has partnered with the Generic Model Organism Database (GMOD) project to obtain funding for a helpdesk and user support. NESCent also co-sponsors the development of GMOD data model extension modules to represent evolutionary data types.

<http://www.gmod.org>

NESCent's funded project Linking Evolution To Genomics Using Phenotype Ontologies involves a partnership with the National Center for Biomedical Ontologies (NCBO) and the Zebrafish Information Network (ZFIN)

<http://www.bioontology.org>

<http://zfin.org>

A pending proposal to develop a digital repository for data in evolutionary biology (DRYAD) involves partnerships with the UNC School of Information & Library Sciences Metadata Research Center, the North Carolina State University Digital Libraries Initiative, the LTER Network and TreeBASE, as well as major evolutionary biology journals and societies, including American Naturalist, Evolution, Society for the Study of Evolution, Integrative and Comparative Biology, Journal of Evolutionary Biology, Molecular Biology and Evolution, Molecular Ecology, Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution, Society of Systematics Biology, National Center for Biotechnology Information, European Society for Evolutionary Biology, German National Library of Science and Technology

<http://ils.unc.edu/mrc/>

<http://www.lib.ncsu.edu/dli/>

<http://www.lternet.edu/>

<http://www.treebase.org>

NESCent worked with the Morphbank and Morphobank projects to promote interoperability.

<http://www.morphbank.net>

<http://morphobank.geongrid.org>

Our INTEROP proposal includes a partnership with the LTER network, NCEAS, the Oak Ridge National Laboratory Distributed Active Archive Center, the USGS National Biological Information Infrastructure and the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF)

<http://www-eosdis.ornl.gov/>

<http://www.nbi.gov>

<http://www.gbif.org>

The Phyloinformatics Hackathon was in partnership with member projects of the Open Bioinformatics Foundation

<http://www.open-bio.org/>

With Google's sponsorship we ran the Phyloinformatics Summer of Code

<http://code.google.com/soc/2007/>

We collaborate with developers at the San Diego Supercomputer Center (SDSC) to define application programming interfaces (APIs) for the CIPRES portal.

<http://www.sdsc.edu>

http://www.phylo.org/sub_sections/portal

Our Summer Courses in Computational Phyloinformatics was with co-sponsorship from CIPRES (Cyberinfrastructure for Phylogenetic Research)

<http://www.phylo.org>

We are a co-sponsor of the Bodega Bay phylogenetics workshop

<http://www.nescent.org/news/thisweek.php?id=58>

We are a co-sponsor of the Analytic Paleontology Summer Course

<http://www.palass.org/modules.php?name=palaeo&sec=careers&page=165>

We are in the process of developing an active collaboration with the Encyclopedia of Life Initiative, with collaborations with their informatics, education and outreach groups, and synthesis center

<http://www.eol.org>

We are collaborating with a set of museum databases (HerpNet, ORNIS, MaNis and BioGeomancer) to help develop a long term plan for expansion, development of community standards and long term sustainability of these valuable databases.

<http://www.herpnet.org/>

<http://www.specifysoftware.org/Informatics/informaticsornis/>

<http://manisnet.org/>

<http://www.biogeomancer.org/>

NESCent has worked with the Australian-New Zealand Research Network for Vegetation Function to co-sponsor a multi day working group on wood evolution. In addition, NESCent, along with NCEAS and QUEST have formed a "Networks International Council;" this group meets by conference call ~2X per year to discuss potential

collaborations and issues.

<http://www.vegfunction.net>

<http://quest.bris.ac.uk/>

We have worked with the Society for the Study of Evolution (SSE) on several projects, including the development of DRYAD and co-sponsorship of NESCent's SACNAS activities. An EOG staff member is a member of the SSE Education Committee.

<http://www.evolutionsociety.org>

The American Institute of Biological Science (AIBS) has been an active partner with NESCent from the start. Currently they are co-sponsors of both the NABT Evolution Symposium and NESCent's SACNAS activities.

<http://www.aibs.org/core/index.html>

NESCent has worked actively with the Ecological Society of America (ESA) in efforts to develop digital data registries and repositories for the evolutionary and ecological sciences. In addition, the ESA is a co-sponsor of our SACNAS activities.

<http://www.esa.org>

We have developed a strong relation with Springer Press. EOG staff members and NESCent Sabbatical Scholars are members of the editorial board of the new Springer journal (Evolution: Education and Outreach). In addition, Springer is providing financial support for NESCent's SACNAS activities.

<http://www.springer.com/east/home/life+sci?SGWID=5-10027-70-173740503-0&detailsPage=journal%7Cdescription>

Sigma Xi, the Scientific Research Society, hosted our 2008 Darwin Day symposium on the Origin and Early Evolution of Life.

<http://www.sigmaxi.org>

NESCent's EOG group is collaborating with the North Carolina Association for Biomedical Research (NCABR) on education and outreach projects.

<http://www.ncabr.org/>

We are participating with the North Carolina Museum of Natural History in their Science Café series.

www.naturalsciences.org

We are participating with the Coalition for the Public Understanding of Science (COPUS) in public education initiatives.

<http://www.copusproject.org>

We worked with the North Carolina School of Science and Math to offer a summer course in teaching evolutionary biology at the elementary school level to teachers.

<http://www.ncssm.edu>

NESCent's EOG is collaborating with Understanding Evolution to produce and distribute monthly Evolution in the News stories and podcasts.

<http://evolution.berkeley.edu/>

NESCent is collaborating with BioQUEST to develop and disseminate modules based on work by NESCent scientists. Modules have been presented at BSA and BioQUEST

workshops.

<http://www.bioquest.org/>

NESCent underwrites the local science radio show, Radio In Vivo, and works with the host, Ernie Hood, to provide media coverage of NESCent events.

<http://radioinvivo.net/>

NESCent partners with the American Museum of Natural History to recruit instructors for their on-line courses.

<http://www.amnh.org/learn/>

NESCent provided support to the NC Science Blogging Conference.

<http://scienceblogging.com>

A NESCent informatics staff member leads the BioSQL project, which, among other things, provides interoperable storage of taxonomies and phylogenetic trees.

<http://biosql.org>

A NESCent informatics staff member was sponsored by the Database Center for Life Science (DBCLS) and the Computational Biology Research Center (CBRC) in Japan to participate in the BioHackathon 2008, which resulted in the first draft of common phyloinformatics web-services.

<http://dbcls.rois.ac.jp/en/>

<http://www.cbrc.jp/index.eng.html>

<http://hackathon.dbcls.jp/>

NESCent is initiating a partnership with the Open Croquet project and the Renaissance Computing Institute (RENCI) to explore innovations for rich and instant collaboration through virtual 3D worlds.

<http://www.opencroquet.org/>

<http://renci.org>

NESCent Informatics is a participant in the NSF-funded TraitNet Research Coordination Network, and within the partnership contributes to the development of trait ontologies and generic semantics-enabled trait databases.

<http://www.columbia.edu/cu/traitnet/>

Appendix 3 Demographics

NESCent applicant data, years 1-3

	Postdoc	Sabbatical Scholars	Short- Term Scholars	Scholar Total	Working Groups	Catalysis Mtgs	Group Totals	Totals
Gender								
Female	46	2	1	3	14	4	18	67
Male	64	22	6	28	35	29	64	156
Gender Unknown	19	2	1	3	0	0	0	22
Residency								
USA	99	18	6	24	45	32	77	200
International	30	8	2	10	4	1	5	45
Race and ethnic identity								
Asian, Pacific Islander	6	1	0	1	2	0	2	9
Black, African- American	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	2
Hispanic	3	0	0	0	0	1	1	4
White, non- Hispanic	53	16	6	22	34	13	47	122
Unknown	57	8	2	10	10	16	26	93
Do not wish to answer	9	1	0	1	2	3	5	15
Total Count	129	26	8	34	49	33	82	245

Demographic data of applicants:

Database includes applicants for postdocs, sabbatical scholars, short-term scholars, and the lead PIs of Working Groups and Catalysis Meetings (this data base has no information on Co-PIs of meeting proposals). Data include applicants from all rounds of proposals, including latest round (December, 2007). All demographic data is self-identification; no demographic data was requested in year 1 (first 2 rounds of applications, accounting for the high "unknown" numbers). Country of residence is the home address of the applicant, and doesn't necessarily reflect citizenship. Shaded columns represent data illustrated in accompanying charts.

Demographic and residency data on NESCent funded scientists

	Postdoc	Sabbatical Scholars	Visiting Scholars	Short- Term	Triangle Scholars	Scholars Total	Triangle Groups	Working Groups	Catalysis Meetings	Group Total	Totals
Gender											
Female	7	1	2	1	3	7	3	11	5	19	33
Male	9	10	4	4	7	25	3	35	21	59	93
Residency											
USA	12	6	5	4	10	25	5	40	22	67	104
International	4	5	1	1	0	7	1	6	4	11	22
Race and ethnic identity											
Asian, Pacific Islander	1	0	1	0	1	2	1	1	1	3	6
Black, African American	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	3
Hispanic	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
White, non-Hispanic	14	11	2	4	8	26	2	25	14	41	80
Unknown	0	0	1	1	1	2	3	19	11	33	36
Citizenship											
US Citizen	12	9	3	3	9	24	3	21	12	36	72
International	4	2	2	1	0	5	0	2	2	4	13
Permanent Resident	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Unknown	0	0	1	1	1	3	3	23	12	38	41
Totals	16	11	6	5	10	32	6	46	26	78	126

Data on NESCent scientists. All data is self-identification. Group PIs include all co-PIs (unlike applicant data set). Data do not include latest round of awards (from December 2007 applicants). Data do not include hosted activities. Shaded columns represent data used in accompanying graphs.

Gender of Applicants

Gender of Awardees

Gender of applicants and awardees. See preceding tables for details of data. Red, female; blue, male; grey, unknown.

Residency of Applicants

Residency of Awardees

Residency of applicants and awardees, years 1-3. Blue, U.S. residents; green, international residents. See demographic tables for specific information.

Ethnic and racial identities of NESCent applicants and awardees

Self-identified ethnic and racial identity of applicants and awardees. Note that in year 1 no demographic data was collected for applicants; and that the specific composition of scholars and group PI is slightly different for applicants and awardees. Applicant data includes December 2007 cohort, but awardees does not include this group. Group PI in awardee data include co-PIs; applicant data do not. Please see preceding tables for data and table captions for details on these categories.

Key for this and following page

Applicants	Awardees
Scholars	
<p>A pie chart for Awardees - Scholars. The chart is divided into six segments: a large light blue segment (approximately 75%), a dark grey segment (approximately 10%), a red segment (approximately 8%), a yellow segment (approximately 4%), an orange segment (approximately 3%), and a very small grey segment (approximately 1%).</p>	
Group PIs	
<p>A pie chart for Awardees - Group PIs. The chart is divided into four segments: a large light blue segment (approximately 65%), a dark grey segment (approximately 25%), a small red segment (approximately 5%), and a very small yellow segment (approximately 1%).</p>	

Appendix 4, Maps

United States Map

of Visits by Funded Participants Based on State of Home Institute

State	Total	State	Total	State	Total	State	Total
Alaska	1	Illinois	27	North Carolina	341	Rhode Island	1
Alabama	1	Indiana	10	Nebraska	3	South Carolina	2
Arizona	21	Kansas	6	New Hampshire	3	South Dakota	7
California	107	Kentucky	1	New Jersey	10	Tennessee	1
Colorado	11	Louisiana	12	New Mexico	9	Texas	19
Connecticut	33	Massachusetts	24	Nevada	2	Utah	4
Washington DC	19	Maryland	19	New York	65	Virginia	13
Florida	26	Maine	2	Ohio	14	Vermont	1
Georgia	19	Michigan	17	Oklahoma	3	Washington	10
Hawaii	8	Minnesota	9	Oregon	13	Wisconsin	5
Iowa	8	Missouri	21	Pennsylvania	27	Wyoming	2
Totals							957

Note: Numbers are not unique visitors (e.g., each visit by an individual appears, so that a participant making multiple visits will appear multiple times). Data only include visitors from NESCent funded activities and does not include hosted meetings.

World Map

of Visits by Funded Participants Based on Country of Home Institute

Country	Total	Country	Total	Country	Total
Australia	9	Italy	1	Panama	3
Bangladesh	1	Jamaica	1	Portugal	1
Brazil	3	Japan	7	Puerto Rico	4
Canada	48	Madagascar	1	Singapore	1
Denmark	4	Mexico	1	Sweden	4
Dominican Republic	2	Netherlands	3	Switzerland	3
Finland	1	New Zealand	2	UK	44
France	5	Norway	1	<i>US</i>	<i>957</i>
Germany	10			<i>Non-US</i>	<i>160</i>
				Totals	1117

Note: Numbers are not unique visitors (e.g., each visit by an individual appears, so that a participant making multiple visits will appear multiple times). Data only include visitors from NESCent funded activities and does not include hosted meetings.

World

Appendix 5, NESCent Funded Awards and Proposals

Funded

Linking Evolution to Genomics Using Phenotype Ontologies

Subaward through University of South Dakota (PI: Paula Mabee)
 National Science Foundation BDI-0641025 (PI: Todd Vision)
 NESCent Total Direct: \$853,338
 NESCent Total Amount: \$1,050,945
 06/01/2007 - 5/31/2010

Enhancement of the GBrowse Genome Annotation Browser

Subaward through University of California at Berkeley (PI: I. Holmes)
 National Institutes of Health (PI: Todd Vision)
 NESCent Total Direct: \$242,565
 NESCent Total Amount: \$310,482 (D&I to UNC),
 4/1/2007 - 3/31/2010

Development of the www.EcoliCommunity.org Information Resource

Subaward through Texas A&M Research Foundation (PI: Jim Hu)
 National Institute of General Medical Science (PI: Todd Vision)
 NESCent Total Direct: \$30,550
 NESCent Total Amount: \$39,104
 06/01/07 – 05/31/09

Pending

A Digital Repository for Preservation and Sharing of Data Underlying Published Works in Evolutionary Biology

National Science Foundation, BD&I (PI: Kathleen Smith)
 NESCent Total Direct: \$1,907,531
 NESCent Total Amount: \$2,180,169 (D&I)
 06/01/08 – 05/31/11

INTEROP: Creation of an International Virtual Data Center for the Biodiversity, Ecological and Environmental Sciences

Subaward through University of New Mexico (PI: William Michener)
 National Science Foundation (PIs: Kathleen Smith and Hilmar Lapp)
 NESCent Total Direct: \$39,535
 NESCent Total Amount: \$50,803
 01/01/08 – 12/31/10

Institute for Museum and Library Sciences

Partnership Agreement through University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill (PI: Jane Greenberg)
 Institute for Museum and Library Sciences
 NESCent cost sharing:

Preliminary Proposals

DataNetONE (Observation Network for Earth)

Subaward through University of New Mexico (PI: William Michener)

National Science Foundation (PI: Kathleen Smith)

NESCent Total Direct: \$117,720

NESCent Total Amount: \$151,270

08/01/08 – 07/31/12

Appendix 6, NESCent Activities Toward the Recruitment of Underserved Groups

The effort to further recruit underrepresented groups into evolutionary biology is a core commitment of the Center and is integrated into all our activities and not the sole responsibility of our EOG group. Our activities include the following:

- Although we are unable to find specific information on the percentage of African-Americans in particular in evolutionary biology, it is clearly very, very low. Nonetheless we have recruited and supported the scientific activities of several outstanding evolutionary biologists, who are also African American. This includes one of our first postdocs, Joe Hereford, a PI of one of our working groups, Paul Magwene, and a visiting scholar, Clara Jones (a faculty member at Fayetteville State University). Scott Edwards and Paul Turner are members of our SAB and Science Review Board.
- One of our Triangle working groups was supported in part because it involved a large number of faculty members from North Carolina Central University, a local Historically Black College/University (HBCU).
- We offer two sabbaticals, a traditional sabbatical and a targeted sabbatical. The latter is specifically targeted towards faculty from minority serving institutions. Targeted sabbaticals provide a higher level of support than traditional ones. To quote our webpage:

What Activities are Currently "Targeted"?

Bringing Evolutionary Biologists from Minority-Serving Institutions to NESCent to lead efforts to increase minority participation in science or develop educational activities

Many Minority-Serving Institutions do not offer sabbaticals. Our fellowships will give these faculty a well-earned chance to reflect, write and research. At the same time, visiting fellows will use their invaluable insights to help us propose ways to increase the number of undergraduates choosing graduate study in evolutionary biology.

IMPORTANT: Applicants from MSU's are not limited to projects that will be undertaken entirely on-site. Proposals involving some bench-work in Triangle labs will be considered. Please contact one of the Directors if you are interested in this possibility

To date we have had two such individuals. The first, John Clamp from North Carolina Central University, among other things, developed twin databases of graduate programs in evolutionary biology and MSIs and other institutions with significant minority enrollment to help connect undergraduates interested in pursuing graduate degrees in evolutionary biology with those programs (available at http://www.nescent.org/eog/minority_serving_institutions.php). The

second, Joe Fail from Johnson C. Smith University developed an evolutionary biology curriculum for elementary schools (see below).

- We have developed a program of undergraduate research internships, in which undergraduates from the participating Universities are recruited to work with postdoctoral fellows and sabbatical scholars at the Center. Thus far, the program has included students from under-represented groups. In the future, we hope to also recruit students from North Carolina Central University.
- We made special efforts to recruit individuals, and classes from MSIs for our Darwin Day symposium, and offered a travel scholarship for students from Johnson C. Smith University.
- Our informatics program offered a summer course this year on Computational Phyloinformatics. Travel awards were made to students from under-represented groups in an attempt to attract additional students from these populations. We are offering such scholarships to other courses such as the Bodega Bay phylogenetics workshop.
- Joe Fail, a targeted sabbatical scholar, produced an exciting and innovative curriculum for teaching evolution in elementary schools. Together with the North Carolina School of Science and Math (a public high school), we obtained funds from Duke University to support a workshop for local teachers on this curriculum. This program was an enormous success, and the School of Science and Math would like to continue this in the future. We are attempting to raise funds to make this a continuing program. The important point of this is that the teachers attending were all from North Carolina public schools and about half of the teachers came from schools where a high percentage of students were minority (32-94%). Obviously improving evolutionary education at this level will have an important impact in the long term.
- Upon the establishment of NESCent, a working group composed of evolutionary biologists from minority serving institutions was convened, Evolution Education at Historically Minority Universities (EEHMU). This group has met twice and outlined the most important issues facing evolution instructors at MSIs and suggested specific activities to address these issues. This year we will work with this group to attempt to obtain funding for an innovative sabbatical program suggested by this group.
- With Scott Edwards, past President of the Society for Systematic Biology, we are developing a program to provide scholarships for faculty and promising undergraduate students from MSIs to attend the annual meeting of the Society for the Study of Evolution.
- We have developed an extremely impressive set of programs for the SACNAS (Society for the Advancement of Chicanos and Native Americans in Science). Two years ago our program was highly lauded by participants and the NSF

program officers in attendance. Last year we expanded our programs and sponsored a field trip to the Kansas Museum of Natural History for a behind the scenes view (there was a lengthy waiting list to participate), a panel discussion on careers in ecology and evolutionary biology, and a showing and discussion of the film “Flock of Dodos”. For this year, we plan to add in student mentoring and graduate school recruitment activities.

- Before coming to NESCent, Jory Weintraub worked with a program at the University of North Carolina which worked to increase the representation of underrepresented groups into the biological and medical sciences. Jory has established a wide range of contacts with teachers from North Carolina MSIs. We have used these contacts for important outreach activities. These activities include recruiting NESCent scientists (primarily postdocs) to travel to these institutions and give guest lectures. This is also an opportunity for undergraduates to talk to relatively young scientists about careers in evolutionary biology. In addition, we have hosted visits by classes from such institutions. For example, this summer a class from NC AT&T visited the center and had brief presentations from postdoctoral fellows Kirsten Fisher, Derrick Zwickl, and Josh Granek. The students had an opportunity to learn more about graduate programs in Evolutionary Biology, ask questions of the postdocs and other NESCent scientists, and participate in a hands-on evolution learning activity led by EOG staff.
- Our evolution in the news podcast program is in part targeted towards students from underrepresented groups. As eloquently expressed by David Hillis in a recent commentary in *Evolution* (“Making Evolution Relevant and Exciting to Biology Students” – *Evolution* 61:1261-1264), new curricular materials and approaches are required to broaden an understanding of evolution. Further, multimedia materials have been successfully used to engage students from underrepresented groups. We are working to target women and minorities as discussants in these podcasts, and actively testing the material in a wide variety of venues including a number of MSIs.
- Two current education working groups - Evolution Across the Curriculum and Tree Reasoning in Evolution Education (TREE) - will also be developing educational resources. The participants in these groups are cognizant of the need to reach underrepresented populations and the relevant issues. We have targeted faculty from MSIs to attend our SELECTION workshop.

In sum, we believe our portfolio of activities to recruit under-represented groups is impressive. It is broad; it spans all activities of the Center and is a core commitment. Most importantly, we believe our chosen activities fit within the core mission of the Center and our abilities to provide effective programs.

Appendix 7, NESCent Organizational Chart - 2008

Appendix 8, NESCent Web Site Information

Total Visitors since January 2007: 37,667

■ Returning Visitors: 19, 813
■ New Visitors: 17, 854

Daily Average: 103 Visits/Day

Weekly Average: 718 Visits / Week

Visitor Home Location

North Carolina (including internal): 15,905

United States (non-North Carolina): 14, 892

International: 6, 870

Most Frequently Visited Pages:

Education and Outreach Home

Science and Synthesis Home

About NESCent

Awards Page

Informatics

NESCent Monthly Web Site Traffic - NC and Other

Month	North Carolina	Other	Total
Jan-07	1492	1,324	2,816
Feb-07	1625	2,067	3,692
Mar-07	1748	2,114	3,862
Apr-07	1642	2,067	3,709
May-07	1532	2,189	3,721
Jun-07	1077	1,458	2,535
Jul-07	833	1,400	2,233
Aug-07	1337	1,483	2,820
Sep-07	1107	1,472	2,579
Oct-07	1450	2,387	3,837
Nov-07	1137	2,165	3,302
Dec-07	925	1,636	2,561
Jan-08	2002	1,862	3,864
Feb-08	937	1,379	2,316
All	18,844	25,003	43,847

Appendix 9
NESCent Representation at Meetings
and
Other Outreach Activities by NESCent Directors and Staff

Year 3 - December 1, 2006 – November 30, 2007

Society and Scientific Meetings:

Society for Integrative and Comparative Biology Meeting, Phoenix, AZ; January 2007
Kathleen Smith; NESCent booth

Society for Molecular Biology and Evolution, Halifax, Nova Scotia, June 24-28, 2007
Todd Vision, Hilmar Lapp, Xianhua Liu; NESCent booth and poster

Society for the Study of Evolution, Christchurch, New Zealand, June 2007
Kathleen Smith, NESCent booth

American Genetics Association, IN, July, 2007
Greg Gibson, poster

Plant Biology and Botany 2007 Joint Congress: Annual Meetings of the American Fern Society (AFS), American Society of Plant Biologists (ASPB), American Society of Plant Taxonomists (ASPT), and Botanical Society of American (BSA), July 7-11, 2007
Todd Vision, Kristin Jenkins; NESCent Booth

American Institute of Biological Sciences 2007 Annual Meeting, Washington, DC, May 13-15, 2007
Jory Weintraub, Kristin Jenkins; NESCent Booth and presentation

International Congress of Vertebrate Morphology, Paris France, July 2007
Kathleen Smith; NESCent poster

Society for Vertebrate Paleontology, Austin Texas, October 2007
Kathleen Smith

European Science Foundation Workshop: Thermal Adaptation in Ectotherms, Barcelona, Spain, March 15-17, 2007
Joel Kingsolver

NOAA Fisheries Symposium and Workshop: Evolutionary Responses to Environmental Change in Salmon, Seattle, WA; December 7-9, 2006
Joel Kingsolver

Informatics Meetings:

Open Repositories 2007, San Antonio, TX, January 22-26, 2007

Hilmar Lapp

GMOD and Genome Database Infrastructure Needs with Evolutionary Model Organism Community, Boston, MA, May 18-19, 2007

Todd Vision

Intelligent Systems for Molecular Biology Conference 2007 (ISMB 2007), Vienna, Austria, July 21-25, 2007

Hilmar Lapp; poster

Education and Outreach Meetings:

National Association of Biology Teachers, Atlanta, GA, November 27-December 2, 2007

Kathleen Smith, Brian Wiegmann, Kristin Jenkins, Jory Weintraub; NESCent Booth, presentation, and sponsorship of the Evolution Symposium

Society for the Advancement of Chicanos and Native Americans in Science (SACNAS), Kansas City, MO, October 10-14, 2007

Kathleen Smith, Jory Weintraub; NESCent EOG activities and booth

Evolution: Education & Outreach (new journal), Springer Editorial Board Meeting, New Orleans, LA, March 2-4, 2007

Joseph Fail, Doug Earnisse, Kristin Jenkins, Jory Weintraub

BioQUEST, Selection Working Group, Beloit College, Beloit, WI; June 9-13, 2007

Jory Weintraub, Kristin Jenkins; participated in BioQUEST workshop, gave presentation on NESCent, and participated in second SELECTION (NESCent) working group meeting, which was being held in conjunction with the BioQUEST workshop.

North Carolina Science Teachers Association, Greensboro, NC, November 14-16, 2007

Jory Weintraub; NESCent booth and presentation

Appendix 10 NESCent Call for Proposals

Announcement Sent to the Following Web Site sand List Serves

1. American Ornithological Union (AOU)
2. American Physiological Society – Comparative & Evolutionary Physiology Section (APS – CEPS)
3. American Society of Ichthyologists and Herpetologists (ASIH)
4. American Society of Mammalogists (ASM)
 - a. Journal On-line
 - b. Web Site
5. Animal Behavior Society (ABS)
6. BIRDNET web site
7. Botanical Society of America (BSA)
8. EvolDir - Evolution Directory (EvolDir)
9. Evolution and Medicine web site
10. Genetics Society of America (GSA)
11. Geological Society of America
12. Paleobotany list serve (through Pat Gensel)
13. Paleontological Society web site
14. Society of Developmental Biology (SDB)
15. Society for Integrative & Comparative Biology (SICB)
16. Society of Molecular Biology and Evolution (SMBE)
17. Society for Study of Evolution (SSE)
 - a. Journal On-line
 - b. Web Site
18. Society of Systematic Biology (SSB)
19. Society for Vertebrate Paleontology (SVP)